

SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDEMSATION OF
p-DIETHYLAMINOBENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE
 HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART IV

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The effect of the substitution of methoxy, ethoxy, chloro and bromo groups in the 6 position of 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylbenzthiazole methiodide has been studied. The absorption and sensitisation spectra of these four substituted dyes have been recorded and compared with those of the unsubstituted dyes. The chemical and other properties have been studied and a few "intermediates" have been described.

It is an established fact that the substitution of different groups in a particular position of a class of cyanine dyes materially affects the sensitising power of the dyes (Mills and Pope, *Phot. J.*, 1920, 44, 183). The inhibition or augmentation of the extra-sensitisation seems to depend upon the characteristics of the group attached. The effect of the substitution of chlorine and bromine atoms in thiocyanines, thiocarbocyanines etc., has been studied by Beilenson and Hamer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1223). They observe that the introduction of one halogen atom into thia-1'-cyanine and thia-2'-cyanine does not affect the absorption. When introduced into the simple thiocarbocyanines, even two halogen atoms have no effect, but with the other kind of dyes e.g. thiacyanine, thiadicarbocyanine and thiatricarbocyanine, the effect of introducing two halogen atoms is to shift the absorption maximum 50-100Å towards the red end. In conclusion they generalise that the shift of the absorption maximum is about the same whether the molecular weight is increased by chlorine or bromine atoms.

On the sensitisation also they observe analogously with Moudgil (*ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1509), that the introduction of a single halogen atom into the molecule has no effect, while two halogen atoms shift the maximum towards the red end by an amount varying from 0-100Å and in some cases the sensitising action is weaker than the corresponding unsubstituted dyes.

In the present work the effect of introducing different groups in a particular position of the *p*-diethylaminostyryl type of cyanine dyes on their absorption and sensitisation has been studied.

For this purpose four new dyes have been prepared by the introduction of methoxy, ethoxy, chloro and bromo groups in the 6 position of 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylbenzthiazole methiodide (I).

The methiodides have in all cases been prepared by heating the base with methyl iodide (1 : 1.5) in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The solids were taken out by dissolving in water, the solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness. The unchanged base was removed by repeated extraction with ether and the residue recrystallised from water.

The syntheses have been effected by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with 5-methoxy-, -5-ethoxy-, -5-chloro- and 5-bromo-benzthiazole methiodides by refluxing the reactants in absolute alcohol using piperidine as a catalyst.

Alcoholic solutions of the first two dyes are reddish in colour, while those of the last two are magenta coloured. The chief characteristics of the dyes have been summarised in Table I.

In column 4 of Table I the pleochroism of the dyes as determined by a polarising microscope (Doja and Prasad, this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 125) has been given.

The first sub-column gives the colour of the crystals in one position of the analyser, the second, after the analyser has been turned through 90°.

The colours of the reflected light from the surface of the crystals are given in column 5, while column 6 shows the comparative intensities of the solutions of the dyes as determined by a Duboscq colorimeter.

Fig. 1

The relative resistances to decolorisation by *N*/100- HCl to 2 c.c. of 1/50,000 solutions of the different dyes in rectified spirit have been determined by titration. The

different titres have been divided by the lowest, and the results given in column 7°.

The frequencies of maximum absorptions, determined by means of a Wedge spectrograph, are given in column 9.

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (cf. Doja, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 348) determined with the help of Wallace colour filters, is given in Table II.

Silk, cotton and wool dyed in the usual way yield shades as are summarised in Table III. Shades thus obtained are washable.

Photographs of sensitisation spectra of these dyes as determined by means of a Wedge spectrograph are shown in Fig. 1.

The absorption spectra like those of other styryl compounds are all single banded (Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1930, 54, 374). The substitution has in all cases depressed the sensitisation. Thus, whereas the unsubstituted 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylbenzthiazole methiodide shows an extra-sensitisation from 5400 Å to 6400 Å (Doja and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 217), the 6-chloro- and 6-bromo-substituted dyes have produced no extra-sensitisation. The alkoxy groups, which generally confer a great extra-sensitisation to the dyes substituted with these groups (vide, K. Mees, "The Theory of Photographic Process", The McMillan Company, New York, 1944, p. 1022), have in the cases studied, produced very little effect. Thus it appears that the extra-sensitisation associated with the substitution of the alkoxy groups, has to a considerable extent been depressed by substitution in the 6 position of the dye.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-6-methoxybenzthiazole methiodide was prepared from 2-methyl-6-methoxybenzthiazole (*Annalen*, 1913, 401, 208) and methyl iodide in 87% yield, m.p. 237°. (Found: I, 39.49. $C_{10}H_{12}ONSI$ requires I, 39.56 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-methoxybenzthiazole Methiodide.—2-Methyl-6-methoxybenzthiazole methiodide (0.321 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.177 g.) and 5 c.c. of absolute alcohol were refluxed with 2 drops of piperidine for 2 hours. The dye which separated out on cooling was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 225°. (Found: N, 5.76; I, 25.61. $C_{21}H_{25}ON_2SI$ requires N, 5.83; I, 26.46 per cent).

2-Methyl-6-ethoxybenzthiazole methiodide was prepared from 2-methyl-6-ethoxybenzthiazole (*Annalen*, 1913, 401, 208) and methyl iodide, m. p. 225°, yield 85%. (Found: I, 37.8. $C_{11}H_{14}ONSI$ requires I, 37.91 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-ethoxybenzthiazole Methiodide.—2-Methyl-6-ethoxybenzthiazole methiodide (0.335 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.177 g.) and absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours with 2 drops of piperidine. The dye that separated on cooling was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 224°. (Found: N, 5.61; I, 25.62. $C_{22}H_{27}ON_2SI$ requires N, 5.67; I, 25.71 per cent).

2-Methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide was prepared from 2-methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole (Beilenson and Hamer, *loc. cit.*) and methyl iodide, m.p. 278°-80°, yield 83%. (Found: I + Cl, 50.13. C_8H_8NSClI requires I + Cl, 49.92 per cent).

TABLE I

Compound.	Yield%.	Form of crystal.	Pleochroism		Reflex.	Relative intensity of colour.	Relative resistance to acid.	Extra-sensitisation		Frequency of max. absorption.
			One position of analyser.	At right angles position of analyser.				Range in λ .	Maximum in λ .	
L	10.4	Mauve felted needles	Deep magenta	Opaque	Nil	1	1	Very little undefinable	×	56620×10^{10}
M	44	Thin magenta needles	Colorless	Fringing at blue	Weak light green	1	1	Very little undefinable	×	58220×10^{10}
N	53.8	Dark shining needles	Maroon	Nearly opaque	Strong green	0.87	2.5	Nil	×	55250×10^{10}
P	22.7	Steel-blue scintillating needles	Yellowish blue	Nearly opaque	Strong yellowish green	0.8	2.7	Nil	×	55910×10^{10}

L—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-methoxybenzthiazole methiodide.

M—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-ethoxybenzthiazole methiodide.

N—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide.

P—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-bromobenzthiazole methiodide.

TABLE II

Wallace colour filter No.	L.	M.	N.	P.
1	Weak red	Cherry-red	Light absorbed	Crimson-red
2	Greenish yellow	Weak red	Claret-red	Pink
3	Weak red	Dull yellow	Rose-red	Weak red
4	Dull yellow	Light absorbed	Pink	Rose-red
5	Dull yellow	Weak yellow	Yellowish pink	Cherry-red
6	Weak red	Lemon-yellow	Rose-red	Very weak red
7	Yellow	Dull yellow	Dull red	Claret-red
8	Yellow	Grass-green	Yellowish red	Orange
9	Dull yellow with orange tinge	Bottle-green	Light absorbed	Weak bluish green
10	Dull yellow with orange tinge	Bottle-green	Orange	Weak red

TABLE III

Dyed on		L.	M.	N.	P.
Cotton	{ Acid bath	Light rose-red	Weak rose-red	Light maroon	Mauve
	{ Neutral	Rose-red	Rose-red	Maroon	Mauve
Silk	{ Acid bath	Pink	Pink	Weak mauve	Weak mauve
	{ Neutral	Pink	Pink	Weak mauve	Weak mauve
Wool	{ Acid bath	Dull pink	Light bluish red	Bluish red	Bluish red
	{ Neutral	Dull pink	Dull pink	Pink	Pink

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-chlorobenzthiazole Methiodide.— 2-Methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide (0.225 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.177 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) were refluxed with 2 drops of piperidine for 4 hours. The separated dye was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 222°. (Found: N, 5.69; I+Cl, 33.44. $C_{20}H_{22}N_2SCl$ requires N, 5.78; I+Cl, 33.54 per cent).

2-Methyl-6-bromobenzthiazole methiodide was prepared from 2-methyl-6-bromobenzthiazole (Beilenson and Hamer, *loc. cit.*) and methyl iodide, m. p. 272-76°, yield 80.5%. (Found: I+Br, 55.96. C_9H_9NSBrI requires I+Br, 56.07 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-bromobenzthiazole Methiodide.— 2-Methyl-6-bromobenzthiazole methiodide (0.371 g), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.177 g.) and absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) were refluxed with 2 drops of piperidine for 4 hours. The dye that separated was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 242°. (Found: N, 5.20; I+Br, 39.11. $C_{20}H_{22}N_2SBrI$ requires N, 5.28; I+Br, 39.24 per cent).

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